
A STUDY OF DIGITAL LIBRARY AND IT'S UTILITY IN EDUCATION

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Abstract:

Human life has become very dynamic. It is constantly changing and changing. Change is an ongoing process. The increasing number of readers, their changing needs and the revolution in reading material led to the division of the library into different types and from that, the emergence and development of electronic library, digital library and virtual library. A digital library is a library that provides improved as well as new services using digital technology. Digital libraries are the collection of all kinds of information available in the world and this information can be accessed through the network (Internet). Similarly, since the information available is in multi-media form, its comprehension is quick

Keywords: Digital libraries, Digital resource, Electronic resource, Education, Digital library Structure.

Introduction:

The computerization of the library during past few decades have focused heavily on the creation of surrogate records of printed documents available in a library or for providing computerized service through secondary databases held locally on CD ROM or magnetic tapes. The scope and functions of integrated library packages, till recently, were essentially

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essentially restricted to providing access to documents at bibliographic level. The new versions of, integrated library packages, however, tend to provide additional features and functionalities akeen to digital libraries. Similarly, secondary information systems such as MEDLINE, INSPEC, COMPENDEX+ and CAS were essentially designed to serve as an effective tools for bibliographic control of research information. However, since these databases provide only bibliographic information on research articles, users had to depend heavily on physical collection available either in their institutional library or on inter-library loan from other libraries for references retrieved from the secondary services. Several attempts were made the in past to make the full-text of research articles available through online search

services, although technology available till late 1980s and early 1990s supported only simple text (ASCII) without graphics. As such, more than 1,700 full-text journals were available through online search services like DIALOG and STN up till 1989 although as simple text without graphics. Tools, techniques and protocols necessary for building-up digital libraries evolved with availability of computing power that allow parallel processing, multitasking, parallel consultation, parallel knowledge navigation and software tools that facilitate artificial intelligence and interactivity. Coincided with the availability of software, hardware and networking technology, the advent of the world wide web (WWW), its ever increasing usage and highly evolved browsers have paved the way for the creation of digital libraries. With rapid developments in the technologies necessary for developing digital libraries, the world of digital information resources has expanded quickly and exponentially. An Increasing number of commercial and society publishers are using the Internet as a global way to offer their publications to the international community of scientists and technologists. Resultantly, increasingly large numbers of STM (Science, Technology and Medical) electronic journals are appearing on the web. Digital information resources include not only rapidly growing collections of electronic full text resources, but also images, video, sound, and even object of virtual reality.

The most significant shift is in building digital collections is greater interoperability among information systems across the networks. With the technology available at an affordable cost, the libraries are initiating small digitization projects as individual library or as a group

of libraries. Building-up digital collection and infrastructure required to access them is a challenge that every library has to deal with. Today's digital libraries are built around Internet and web technologies with electronic journals as their building blocks. The increasing popularity of Internet and developments in web technologies are catalyst to the concept of digital libraries. is a pictorial representation of digital library infrastructure and services that can be generated from them.

Growth and developments in digital libraries can generally be attributed to emergence of Internet, particularly world wide web (WWW) as a media of information delivery and access, availability of highly evolved, extraordinarily simple and intuitive user interface, ie. Internet Explorer and Chrome and advances in online storage technologies enabling storage of large amounts of contents at increasingly affordable cost. The product and services that goes into digital library comes from electronic publishing.

Digital Library: Towards A Definition:

Terence R. Smith (1997), defined digital libraries as “controlled collections of information bearing objects (IBOs) that are in digital form and that may be organized, accessed, evaluated and used by means of heterogeneous and extensible set of distributed services that are supported by digital technology”

Clifford Lynch (1995), a well-know expert on digital libraries and new technologies, defined digital library as “a system providing a community of users with coherent access to a large, organized repository of digital information and knowledge. The digital library is not just one entity, but multiple sources seamlessly integrated.”

- Providing accessibility to huge quantities of content to its users independent of location and as per convenience

- Providing accessibility to main information resources

Structure of Digital Library:

From the above diagram, two important parts of digital library can be found, one is digital and the other is digital library. Information is stored in the library

and delivered to the reader through communication technology and appropriate location.

Considering the digital library, it is noticed. That is, on the one hand, the information we have made in digital format. The other is to get your readers using computer and communication technology, but the other is the reading literature in your library. To digitize it and make it available to all other communities.

Functions of Digital Library:

As mentioned by patra and nahak 2014, the major function of digital libraries are:

- Providing assessibility to huge quantities of content to its users independent of location and as per convenience
- Providing accessibility to main information resources.
- Supporting the multimedia information besides the text
- Providing user-friendly interface
- Highly developed search and consequent recovery

- To authorize the data provided for improving the reliability of the digital library
- To substantiate knowledge for updating the learning
- To offer responsive interfaces to its users
- To reward with further network functionalities
- To improve the advanced searching, accessing and recovery of data
- To protect the user information

Benefits of Digital Libraries for In Education:

Libraries have always been a crucial part of the learning process. One can describe the library as a centrally organized set consisting of resources that include an entire spectrum of different types of media (text, video, hypermedia) as well as human services. When we think about libraries, the first thing that comes to mind is the physical components such as space, equipment, storage, racks full of books and other academic material. No one can deny the role reading play in the life of students. Since digitization has taken over most of the components in education, learning through digital libraries is not a thing of the past anymore. The decline in visits to conventional libraries suggests that students prefer to access information and read content without visiting a library in person. While many libraries and universities are digitizing their materials to be accessible to members and the general public, let us take a look at the main benefits of digital libraries for in education:

Instant access to resources: There is no luxury such as having access to abundant knowledge and relevant information pertaining to specific subjects. A Digital library cuts short the time and

effort one would put into visiting a conventional library and finding the right book. With options like in-built content search with only a few keywords or titles, searching for what you need from thousands of resources becomes easy. No physical boundaries: Accessing the digital library is much easier and efficient, unlike a conventional library, students don't have to check the opening and closing hours to plan their visits; with just an internet connection, you can access a digital library anytime, anywhere. Digital libraries provide the students with the convenience of learning at their own comfort. Students can access and read the library materials in various digital formats (eBooks, audio books, videos on demand 24 hrs/day) anytime and anywhere using their preferred devices.

Preservation of resources: Conventional libraries need to invest heavily in the maintenance and preservation of library resources. The physical library resources are accessed and reused by readers regularly, where it becomes difficult to prevent the deterioration of books, vinyl records, cassette tapes and other resources. Whereas with digital libraries, the content is digitized, and the digital resources are accessible to a large number of readers regularly without focusing on the preservation of physical materials. **Real-Time Interactions:** One of the main benefits of using the digital library is that students can clarify their doubts then and there with new-age management software that can facilitate interaction between readers and administrators. The readers can also interact by setting up online communities and find a resolution to their doubts in real-time. This dynamic and real-time interaction feature has the potential to

make the readers switch from conventional libraries to digital libraries.

Updated information: Digital libraries help you access the updated resources with the latest technology available, the conventional libraries may fall behind in purchasing the latest editions of books, magazines, and other content resources. But digital libraries in education institutes or organizations can update the digital library regularly. Many publishers these days allow digital libraries to make the latest editions and magazines accessible to the readers based on the pay-as-you-read model. Hence, digital libraries help engage readers by providing access to the latest publications

Name of Some Digital Libraries:

- NSDL – NATIONAL SCIENCE DIGITAL LIBRARY
- DLI – DIGITAL LIBRARY OF INDIA
- ICDL- INTERNATIONAL CHILDREN DIGITAL LIBRARY
- TKDL – TRADITIONAL KNOWLEDGE DIGITAL LIBRARY
- LDL – LIBRARIES DIGITAL LIBRARY

Conclusion:

The primary function of any academic library is to provide quality information service in order to satisfy their users with the right information at the right time. The achievement of digital library is really helpful in order to fulfill the requirement of users. Digital library offers

many option to the library users to do the task as quickly as possible. Use of the digital library enables the library to save space of the library and save time of the users. Although there are some challenges that users are facing while using the digital library. To meet these challenges librarians should play an important role. The library should possess to have well trained library staff who can guide the users and can teach them how to use the digital resources. Most important thing librarian should do efforts to create more awareness among users about digital resources.

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